

Relative performance of *Bt* and their corresponding non-*Bt* cotton genotypes for sucking pests and yield

VIJANDER PAL, P. D. SHARMA, S. L. JAT AND RAHUL CHAUHAN

Department of Entomology, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

ABSTRACT : Performance of eight *Bt* and their corresponding non-*Bt* cotton hybrids for sucking pests and yield was studied at Research Farm of CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. *Bt*-genotypes MRC-6301 (0.91 nymphs/leaf), ANKUR-2226 (0.92 nymphs/leaf) and MRC-6304 (0.93 nymphs/leaf) and non-*Bt* genotypes ANKUR-2534 (0.88 nymphs/leaf), MRC-6304 (0.91 nymphs/leaf) and RCH-317 (0.88 nymphs/leaf) harboured less leaf hopper population as compared to others under unprotected conditions. While under protected conditions *Bt* genotypes RCH-138 (0.65 nymphs/leaf), RCH-317 (0.75 nymphs/leaf) and non-*Bt* genotypes MRC-6304 (0.76 nymphs/leaf) and ANKUR-2534 (0.77 nymphs/leaf) had less population. Regarding whitefly under unprotected conditions, the genotypes RCH-138 *Bt* (0.46 adults/leaf), MRC-6301 *Bt* (0.47 adults/leaf) and RCH-138 non-*Bt* (0.41 adults/leaf) and MRC-6301 non-*Bt* (0.42 adults/leaf) supported less population. In protected conditions, the entries RCH-138 *Bt* (0.49 adults/leaf), ANKUR-2534 *Bt* (0.51 adults/leaf), ANKUR-2534 non-*Bt* (0.52 adults/leaf) and RCH-134 non-*Bt* (0.56 adults/leaf) recorded low population. The yield of seed cotton was higher in *Bt* genotypes than their corresponding non-*Bt* genotypes. In *Bt* genotypes, the yield ranged between 13.71 to 27.84 q/ha with an average of 19.78 q/ha and 13.02 to 26.47 q/ha with an average of 18.64 q/ha under unprotected and protected conditions, respectively. In non-*Bt* genotypes the yield ranged between 4.66 to 12.75 q/ha with an average of 8.50 q/ha; 5.34 to 14.39 q/ha with an average of 10.43 q/ha under unprotected and protected conditions, respectively.

Key words : *Bt* and non-*Bt* cotton genotypes, protected and unprotected, sucking pests

India is amongst the major cotton growing countries of the world and ranks 1st in global scenario (about 20% of the world cotton area) by growing cotton on 8.5-9.0 million hectares, but productivity-wise the country ranks 2nd after China by producing 31.5 million bales during 2007-2008 (Anonymous, 2008). As regards Indian situation, the average yield has been poor calling for attention towards improvement in performance of cotton genotypes in stress situation and crop management in the situations of deficit rainfall, heavy attack of insect pests and their non effective control measures and non-judicious use of insecticides. The insect-pests are known to cause 56-60 per cent reduction in yield (Sharma, 1998) but during favourable weather (medium temperature and relative humidity) the damage may reach any height. After the introduction of *Bt* cotton, the damage due to sucking pests is a serious concern. Among the sucking insects of economic importance, leafhopper, *Amrasca bigutulla bigutulla* (Ishida) and whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) are the most important and have been reported to cause serious quantitative and qualitative losses.

The studies were carried out under unprotected and protected conditions at

Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University Farm, Hisar during *kharif* season of 2003. The 16 genotypes comprising eight *Bt* hybrids (ANKUR-651 *Bt*, RCH-134 *Bt*, MRC-6301 *Bt*, ANKUR-2226 *Bt*, RCH-138 *Bt*, ANKUR-2534 *Bt*, MRC-6304 *Bt* and RCH-317 *Bt*) and their corresponding non-*Bt* hybrids. The sowing of these different genotypes was done in the month of May, with spacing of 67.5 x 60 cm. Each treatment was placed in randomized block design replicated three times. The weekly observations were recorded on the population of sucking pests. Population counts of these sucking pests were taken from the three fully formed leaves from upper, middle and lower canopy of each of five randomly selected plants.

Studies on the relative performance of *Bt* and their corresponding non-*Bt* genotypes (Table 1) indicated that the mean population of cotton leafhopper under unprotected conditions was higher in RCH-134 *Bt* (1.05 nymphs/leaf), ANKUR-2534 *Bt* (1.02 nymphs/leaf), RCH-317 *Bt* (0.96 nymphs/leaf), and minimum in MRC-6301 *Bt* (0.91 nymphs/leaf), while in non-*Bt* the maximum population was recorded in RCH-138 (1.00 nymphs/leaf) and ANKUR-651 (1.00 nymphs/leaf) and minimum in ANKUR-2534

Table 1. Relative performance of *Bt* and their corresponding non-*Bt* genotypes towards incidence of cotton leafhopper, *Amrasca bigutulla bigutulla* (Ishida) and whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius), under unprotected and protected conditions during kharif 2003

Genotype	*Mean number of nymphs/leaf							
	Unprotected conditions				Protected conditions			
	<i>Bt</i>		Non- <i>Bt</i>		<i>Bt</i>		Non- <i>Bt</i>	
	Leafhopper	Whitefly	Leafhopper	Whitefly	Leafhopper	Whitefly	Leafhopper	Whitefly
ANKUR-651	0.95	0.51	1.00	0.46	0.96	0.66	0.83	0.59
RCH-134	1.05	0.53	0.98	0.49	0.87	0.66	0.86	0.56
MRC-6301	0.91	0.47	0.91	0.42	0.91	0.58	0.78	0.56
ANKUR-2226	0.92	0.49	0.96	0.44	0.97	0.60	1.04	0.59
RCH-138	0.94	0.46	1.00	0.41	0.65	0.49	0.98	0.58
ANKUR-2534	1.02	0.53	0.88	0.58	0.85	0.51	0.77	0.52
MRC-6304	0.93	0.55	0.88	0.53	1.03	0.66	0.76	0.59
RCH-317	0.96	0.49	0.88	0.54	0.75	0.64	0.85	0.63
Mean	0.96	0.50	0.94	0.48	0.87	0.60	0.85	0.58

*Mean of 14 weeks (26th-39th standard weeks, 6 August-30 September).

(0.88 nymphs/leaf) and MRC-6304 (0.88 nymphs/leaf). In protected conditions, the mean population of leaf hopper among *Bt* genotypes was maximum in MRC-6304 *Bt* (1.03 nymphs/leaf), ANKUR-2534 *Bt* (0.85 nymphs/leaf) and ANKUR-651 *Bt* (0.96 nymphs/leaf) and minimum in RCH-138 *Bt* (0.65 nymphs/leaf) and RCH-317 (0.75 nymphs/leaf). Among non-*Bt* genotypes, the mean population was maximum in ANKUR-2226 (1.04 nymphs/leaf), RCH-138 (0.98 nymphs/leaf) and RCH-134 (0.86 nymphs/leaf) and minimum in MRC-6304 (0.76 nymphs/leaf). The data are in conformity with the observations reported earlier (Simwat and Dhawan, 1994; Dhawan, 2000; Vennila *et al.*, 2004; Aggarwal *et al.*, 2007).

The mean population of cotton whitefly under unprotected conditions was higher in MRC-6304 *Bt* (0.55 adults/leaf), RCH-134 (0.53 adults/leaf) and ANKUR-2534 *Bt* (0.53 adults/leaf) and ANKUR-651 *Bt* (0.51 adults/leaf) and minimum in RCH-138 *Bt* (0.46 adults/leaf), while in non-*Bt* the maximum population was recorded in ANKUR-2534 (0.58 adults/leaf), and minimum in ANKUR-2226 (0.44 adults/leaf). In protected conditions, the mean population among *Bt* genotypes was maximum in MRC-6304 *Bt* (0.66 adults/leaf), RCH-134 *Bt* (0.66 adults/leaf) and ANKUR-651 *Bt* (0.66 adults/leaf) and minimum in RCH-138 *Bt* (0.49 adults/leaf). The mean population among non-*Bt* genotypes was maximum in RCH-317 (0.63 adults/leaf), and minimum in ANKUR-2534 (0.52 adults/leaf).

These observations are in agreement with the observations reported earlier by Gupta *et al.* (2001) and Aggarwal *et al.* (2007).

With respect to yield under unprotected conditions in *Bt* genotypes, the maximum was recorded in RCH 134 *Bt* (27.84 q/ha) followed by RCH 317 *Bt* (25.09 q/ha), whereas in non-*Bt* genotypes, ANKUR-2226 (12.75 q/ha) and ANKUR-2534 (11.38 q/ha) outyielded the others. Under protected conditions *Bt* genotypes RCH 317 *Bt* (26.47 q/ha) and RCH 138 *Bt* (25.23 q/ha) yielded higher and in non-*Bt* genotypes ANKUR-2226 (15.77 q/ha) and RCH-317 (12.77 q/ha) (Table 2) gave higher yield. These results derive support from earlier reports by Khadi and Kulkarni (1998) as well as Qaim and Zilberman (2002).

Table 2. Yield of *Bt* and their corresponding non-*Bt* genotypes under unprotected and protected conditions during kharif 2003

Genotype	Yield of seed cotton (q/ha)			
	Unprotected conditions		Protected conditions	
	<i>Bt</i>	Non- <i>Bt</i>	<i>Bt</i>	Non- <i>Bt</i>
ANKUR-651	19.20	10.01	13.02	11.24
RCH-134	27.84	9.46	22.49	11.24
MRC-6301	18.65	6.30	17.41	8.77
ANKUR-2226	17.28	12.75	15.77	14.39
RCH-138	21.12	4.66	25.23	9.73
ANKUR-2534	13.71	11.38	16.18	8.63
MRC-6304	15.35	5.24	13.98	5.34
RCH-317	25.09	8.22	26.47	12.77
Mean	19.78	8.50	18.64	10.43

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, N., Brar, D. S. and Butter, G. S. 2007.** Evaluation of *Bt* and non-*Bt* version of two cotton hybrids under different spacing against sucking insect-pests and natural enemies. *J. Cotton Res. Dev.* **21** : 106-10.
- Anonymous, 2008.** *Annual Report.* All India Co-ordinated Cotton Improvement Project, 2008-2009, CICR, Nagpur.
- Dhawan, A. K. 2000.** Cotton pest scenario in India : Current status of insecticides and future perspectives. *Agrolook* **1** : 9-26.
- Gupta, G. P., Janakiraman, S., Raghuraman, M. and Singh, R. P. 2001.** Status of transgenic cotton and its prospect in India. *Agrolook* **2** : 7-19.
- Khadi, B. M. and Kulkarni, V. N. 1998.** Future research needs for improving yields and qualities of farmers under rainfed conditions Proc. Natl. Sem. Strategies for Improvement of Production, Productivity and Quality of Cotton, Mumbai, 4-5 May. pp. 14.
- Gaim, M. and Zilberman, D. 2002.** Yield effects of genetically modified crops in developing countries. *Science Washington*. pp. 900-02.
- Sharma, P. D. 1998.** Estimation of yield losses due to insect-pests on cotton. *Annual Report.* All India Co-ordinated Cotton Improvement Project, 1997-1998, CCSHAU, Hisar.
- Simwat, G. S. and Dhawan, A. K. 1994.** Changing pest status of cotton in relation to change in crop production and protection technologies in Punjab. *J. Cotton Res. Dev.* **8** : 112-21.
- Vennila, S., Panchbhai, P. R., Biradar, V. K., Gadpayle, J. G., Ramteke, M. S., Deole, S. A. and Karanjakar, P. P. 2004.** Growth and survival of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) and *Spodoptera litura* (Boisd.) on transgenic *Bt* cotton. *J. Cotton Res. Dev.* **19** (1).

Received for publication : October 5, 2009